

FE-BASED PREDICTION OF THE NONLINEAR IN-PLANE SHEAR RESPONSE OF WOVEN LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: A predictive approach for the mechanical behavior of woven laminates is presented and applied to a twill-weave carbon fiber reinforced composite laminate subjected to in-plane shear. The woven architecture is initially considered and a representative volume identified. A 3D finite element model of the representative volume is developed defining appropriate boundary conditions to enforce continuity and periodicity in stresses and strains. Stiffness and damage evolution up to final rupture of the model laminate under in-plane shear loading is determined on the basis of the properties of the constitutive materials and of a damage model. The computational results are discussed in the light of parallel experiments on actual composite laminates. Modeling issues affecting predicted stiffness and strength are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: woven composites, representative volume, finite element method, in-plane shear, twill-weave, stiffness, damage evolution.

INTRODUCTION

Woven-fiber composite materials represent a type of textile composite where strands are formed by the process of weaving, [1]. These strands are interlaced in two mutually orthogonal (warp and fill) directions to one another and impregnated with a resin material. Woven composite laminates are characterized by such advantages as balanced in-plane mechanical properties, improved impact resistance and easy handling and shaping. They are increasingly used in the fabrication of advanced structures in the aerospace, naval construction or automotive sectors. There is a wide range of possible architectures and constituents to be used with this class of composites, because it is possible to act on microstructural geometry, weave type, hybridization or choice of constituents, [2].

To select the best possible combination of weight, cost, stiffness and strength properties of a woven-fiber composite, a detailed understanding of the link between material structure and mechanical performance is required. Therefore development of predictive tools of the 3D elastic and strength properties of woven-fiber composite materials has been the subject of extensive research, [1]. In the last two decades computational approaches adopting mainly the finite element method have been extensively used to model the mechanics of woven composite laminates, see for example [3] for a review.

Due to their popularity, computational studies have mostly considered i) the carbon fiber reinforcement ii) the plain-weave texture and iii) the tensile response in the yarn direction, [4-8]. Factors such as yarn curvature, number of plies, stacking sequence etc., on the global stiffness of fabric laminates were quantified, [5]. Computational procedures for modeling the damage and strength response of such materials have also been proposed and applied but not yet completely validated, [4, 6-7]. The present authors have investigated also the tensile response of the twill weave texture using a computational approach, [8].

This paper deals with the application of a finite-element based approach to the prediction of the stiffness and strength of a woven carbon fiber reinforced composite laminate subjected to in-plane shear. Therefore the approach is initially outlined starting with the procedure for the development of a representative volume (RV) required to describe the repetitive geometry of a weave. The finite element model of the RV, the boundary conditions, the constitutive material models and the strategies for damage and failure description are discussed next. The paper ends with the discussion of computational results of stiffness and strength.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A series of steps are followed to develop a finite element model of a woven composite: i) definition of a representative volume (RV) of the woven composite; ii) finite element modeling of the RV; iii) definition of boundary conditions for the RV; iv) selection and application of material and damage models.

Representative volume (RV)

Woven lamina is obtained by interlacing yarns (or strands) in two mutually orthogonal (warp and fill) directions according to a predefined scheme. Fig. 1 shows the twill-weave texture. Each yarn is formed by thousands of reinforcing fibers (here carbon fibers). A structural laminate is obtained by laying up a number of laminas, each with its own specific orientation in a mold to obtain a desired 3D shape. The laminate is then processed, i.e. cured in an oven. After polymerization the laminate is cut to the desired form and finished.

Fig. 1: Twill-weave texture and RVE

Fig. 2: Idealized cross-section and definition of architectural parameters of a twill-weave lamina.

From the finite element modeling point of view, the repetitive nature of a texture suggests the identification of a so-called representative volume, RV. It can be thought of as the building block of the lamina and of the laminate by multiplication in the different spatial directions of the RV. The RV for a twill weave is identified in Fig. 1. The cross-section of the twill weave lamina, shown in Fig. 2, presents the idealized fill and warp yarn geometry and the important

dimensions. Both straight and curved portions of the yarns characterize the twill weave texture. The epoxy matrix envelops the yarn fibers and fills the voids at the edges of the yarn intersections. The geometrical model of the RV is then meshed into finite elements using 3D brick and wedge elements. To describe the complex architecture, however, model development involves geometrical simplifications of the yarn curvature and the yarn cross-section, [5,6]. In any case thousands of finite elements are required for 3D models such that of Fig. 3 (i.e. 80000).

Fig. 3: 3D finite element model of the twill-weave RV and detail of yarn geometry and mesh

Fig. 4: Reference points, sides and edges of the RV to be used in boundary condition specification.

Boundary conditions on RV

The finite element analysis of an RV is aimed at obtaining the macroscopic (global) response of a laminate, i.e. an ideal infinite medium subjected to uniform boundary conditions, either in stresses or displacements. Appropriate boundary conditions must be applied to the RV model to simulate the presence of the adjacent RV in the same plane (for a single lamina) and of other RV positioned above and below (for a thick laminate). Therefore boundary conditions that generate local (microscopic) stress and strain fulfilling the periodicity of the heterogeneous material have to be specified. Following ref. [9] the displacement fields $\underline{u}(\underline{x})$ inside the RV is assumed to be related to the strain fields by the following general equation, [10],

$$\underline{u}(\underline{x}) = \underline{u}^o + \underline{\Omega}\underline{x} + \underline{E}\underline{x} + \tilde{\underline{u}}(\underline{x}) \quad (1)$$

where the first two terms, \underline{u}^o and $\underline{\Omega}$, are rigid body displacement and rotation of the RV, respectively, \underline{E} the macroscopic homogenous strain on RV and $\tilde{\underline{u}}(\underline{x})$ is the periodic part of the displacement field, which is associated to a periodic strain with zero average value. The following equations were preliminarily defined so that all corresponding nodes on the opposite sides behave like the mid reference nodes defined in Fig. 4, [9],

$$\underline{u}^A - \underline{u}^C = \underline{u}^L - \underline{u}^M \quad (2)$$

$$\underline{u}^B - \underline{u}^D = \underline{u}^J - \underline{u}^K \quad (3)$$

where L and M are corresponding nodes on opposite sides defined by $x_3 = l_3$ e $x_3 = 0$, J and K are corresponding nodes on opposite sides defined by $x_1 = l_1$ e $x_1 = 0$ and P and Q are corresponding nodes on opposite sides defined by $x_2 = h$ e $x_2 = 0$

Eqns. (2) and (3) simulate the presence of other RVs in the 1, 2 and 3 coordinate directions. An additional reference node, E, is identified in the middle of the $x_2 = 0$ side of the RV. The relationships for eliminating rigid body motions of the model can be found elsewhere, [8]. In this work in-plane shear was applied to the RV simply enforcing u_i displacement components of equal magnitude but opposite sign to the reference points A e C, see Fig. 4. A view of the RV in its undeformed and deformed (i.e. magnified) conditions is presented in Fig. 5 along with the definition of macroscopic in-plane shear strain E_{13} .

Fig. 5: Top view of undeformed and deformed RV under in-plane shear

Fig. 6: In-plane shear stress σ_{13} distribution in the RV

Constitutive laws

The mechanical response of a woven lamina is obtained from the mechanical properties of the constituent materials (i.e. carbon fiber yarns and epoxy matrix). The polymer matrix has an important role in the shear response of woven laminates and was assumed homogeneous and isotropic with an elastic stress-strain response defined by a Young's modulus $E = 4.4$ GPa; Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.34$; tensile strength $S = 159$ MPa. The fiber yarn was assumed transversely isotropic linear elastic whose mechanical properties are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Elastic properties and directional strengths of the carbon fiber yarns, [4]

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}, ν_{13}	ν_{23}	S_{11} (MPa)	S_{22}, S_{33} (MPa)	S_{12}, S_{13} (MPa)	S_{23} (MPa)
150	10	5.7	3.4	0.3	0.5	2550	152	97	55

Macroscopic response

A homogenization procedure is applied to determine the macroscopic in-plane shear stresses and shear strain (Σ_{13}, E_{13}) representative of the lamina response on the basis of the relevant computed stress distributions, [10]. By way of example, Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the microscopic shear stress σ_{13} in the RV superposed on the deformed model. To obtain the corresponding Σ_{13} at the end of each load increment the following integral is computed

$$\Sigma_{13} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma_{13} dV \quad (4)$$

The corresponding macroscopic shear strain E_{13} (i.e. half of the engineering shear strain γ_{13}) is determined directly from the displacement components of the reference nodes.

$$E_{13} = \frac{u_1^A - u_1^C}{l_3} \quad (5)$$

Inspection of Fig. 6 reveals the periodicity of stress and displacements over the RV and the presence of a heterogeneous stress distribution within the fiber yarns.

Damage modeling

The finite element analysis of the RV is nonlinear as a procedure for the simulation of the damage initiation and evolution is implemented into the finite element code. Therefore the RV boundary is displaced incrementally and the microscopic stress and strain fields ($\underline{\sigma}(\underline{x})$, $\underline{\epsilon}(\underline{x})$) are determined at the end of each time increment. The matrix is assumed to be isotropically brittle and the maximum principal stress criterion is applied. When, during the loading phase, the matrix strength is locally exceeded, the elastic properties of the matrix are modified, i.e. reduced, element-by-element, of a predefined amount, [4].

The yarns are assumed to be made of perfectly bonded fiber and matrix and four different damage mechanisms are considered, [7]. Referring to the principal material directions of the fiber yarn (i.e. longitudinal L, and transverse T and S), the mechanism L is dominated by fiber break. The other mechanisms are associated to fractures of the epoxy within the yarn caused by different stress components. Mechanisms L and T are controlled by normal longitudinal and transverse stresses, while mechanisms LT, SL and TS are controlled by the corresponding shear stresses. During the loading phase, the local stresses in the yarns are determined at each integration point of every finite element, then referred to the local material directions and compared to the directional strengths X_{ij} . When a specific directional strength is exceeded, that is

$$\sigma_{ij} = X_{ij} \quad \text{where } i, j = L, T, S \quad (6)$$

The corresponding elastic modulus q_{ij} is discounted of a prescribed amount D_{ij} , according to the relationships

$$q_{ijD} = q_{ij} D_{ij} \quad \text{where } i, j = L, T, S \quad (7)$$

Table 2: Degradation coefficients of the elastic properties of the fiber yarn [4].

	D_{LL}	D_{TT}	D_{SS}	D_{LT}	D_{LS}	D_{TS}
MECHANISM L	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
MECHANISM T	1.0	1.0	0.01	1.0	0.2	0.2
MECHANISM S	1.0	0.01	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.2
MECHANISM LT	1.0	1.0	0.01	1.0	0.01	1.0
MECHANISM LS	1.0	0.01	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.01
MECHANISM TS	1.0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01

The parameters D_{ij} associated to the different yarn damage mechanisms defined in Table 2 are based on experimental considerations, [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In-plane shear stiffness

The present computational modeling using an RV allows the direct estimation of the shear stiffness of both the lamina and a laminate thus determining the influence of the structural parameters. For the case of direct tension, [8], the role of crimp ratio, number of plies, constituents on the stiffness was estimated and found to agree with experimental evidence. The present numerical model has the same yarn cross-section and crimp ratio (undulation) of an experimental material as determined by specimen sectioning, polishing and optical measurements, [8]. The predicted moduli of elasticity in shear obtained under the single lamina and the thick laminate assumptions are presented in Table 3, along with a reference experimental result obtained with an eight-ply laminate, [11]. Inspection of Table 3 reveals that the model predicts that the lamina is less stiff than the thick laminate because of the different degrees of constraint to the out-of-plane displacement. The experimental result is closer to the thick laminate case.

Table 3: In-plane modulus of elasticity in shear for a twill-weave architecture

	Experimental	RV Lamina	RV Laminate
G_{13} (GPa)	3.753	3.287	4.050

In-plane shear strength

Strength prediction by the finite element approach is complex, as the damage processes in the RV have to be simulated. The shear stress distribution in the RV due to an in-plane shear load of Fig. 6 demonstrates the degree of nonuniformity within the single yarn and between yarn and matrix. Therefore damage evolution in a twill-weave lamina during shear loading is now discussed in terms of: i) activation and evolution of damage mechanism and ii) global stress-strain curve up to ultimate failure.

Fig. 8 presents damage evolution in the fiber yarns. In black are characterized the finite elements where a local failure criterion is exceeded. Shear stress concentrates initially at the yarn edges, especially where they are crimped (bent out of plane by the weave architecture). Therefore damage starts at the yarn intersection and spreads in both yarns in the radial direction (Fig. 8a and 8b). As the deformation increases damage tends to concentrate along preferred directions associated to the weave pattern (Fig. 8c and 8d).

As for the global shear strain vs. shear stress response, previous tests of woven laminates, [11], demonstrated that the behavior is nonlinear from the beginning of the test because possibly the contribution of inter-yarn and inter-ply epoxy layers to deformation and damage. The present modeling approach is assessed comparing directly the computed shear stress vs. shear strain response and a reference experimental curve in Fig. 9. The experimental trend is smoothly nonlinear while the predicted trend shows large drops in stress possibly due to a sudden failure of a large portion of the model under displacement-controlled loading conditions. Obviously in the model every RV of a specimen behaves identically while in practice a uniform material response is not expected.

Fig. 8: Evolution of damage in the fiber yarns with applied load

Actually two predicted responses are introduced in Fig. 9 for a twill-weave architecture. They are obtained by slightly different finite element models of the RV. The first is obtained using a finite element model optimized for tensile loading of a lamina and whose results were discussed in [8]. It is characterized by a linear response and an over prediction of stress at first failure.

Fig. 9: Comparison of shear stress vs. shear strain curves for the twill-weave architecture

A limit of the RV model was the absence of an epoxy layer between orthogonal yarns, which is not important for tensile loading but it was believed to stiffen the response under in-plane shear. Therefore for this work a thin layer of matrix elements was inserted between orthogonal yarns of the model and the initially nonlinear response of the experiment is obtained. Nonetheless, stress drops are still found during loading of the RV model. Computational works by other researchers, [7], show this kind of trend in predicted responses beyond the first failure event. Although these new results demonstrate the potential of the proposed approach, a number of modeling issues still need clarification.

CONCLUSIONS

A predictive method of the mechanical properties of woven fabric laminates based the finite element method has been presented and applied to the in-plane shear response of a carbon-fiber-reinforced, twill-weave lamina. The model predicts both stiffness and strength of the woven composite on the basis of the representative volume of the weave, the mechanical properties of the constituents (i.e. fiber yarn and epoxy matrix) and a damage accumulation approach. The predictive capability of the proposed method was verified using the elastic behavior and the shear stress vs. shear strain curves obtained with experiments on actual carbon fiber reinforced laminates. The elastic behavior of the woven laminate is well described by the model. However the typical nonlinear response to failure of woven laminates loaded in shear is only partially captured by the present model.

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